

Insurance Premium

April 28, 2026

1 Description

InsureYou, an insurance company, sets premiums based on the risk of heart disease, charging higher premiums for high-risk patients.

1) **InsureYou relies on employees to assess an applicant's risk of developing heart disease.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of InsureYou. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the risk of developing heart disease?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the risk of developing heart disease.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the risk of developing heart disease

MedForYou, a medical organization, collects data (such as age, sex, blood pressure, cholesterol, smoking habits, etc.) from patients with depression. MedForYou uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict the likelihood of a patient developing a heart disease.

2) **Instead of employees, the InsureYou now relies on MedForYou's AI to assess an applicant's risk of developing heart disease.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of InsureYou. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the risk of developing heart disease?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable

v) completely acceptable

- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the risk of developing heart disease.
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the risk of developing heart disease.

3) **Consider that InsureYou relies on MedForYou’s AI to assess an applicant’s risk of developing heart disease and calculate their insurance premiums. MedForYou identified an issue with its AI where it offers lower premiums to brunettes over non-brunettes, even if they have a high risk. To address this, MedForYou modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how ‘the AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c) and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts higher premiums for low risk applicants. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still provide correct insurance premiums for low risk applicants. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for MedForYou to choose?**

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes; otherwise, it provides the correct insurance premiums.
- ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it provides slightly incorrect insurance premiums.
- iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it provides moderately incorrect insurance premiums.
- iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it provides highly incorrect insurance premiums

- Give an example of potential issues if MedForYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that InsureYou can learn whether an applicant has depression by identifying if they were part of MedForYou’s data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still prevent InsureYou from identifying an applicant has depression. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for MedForYou to choose?**

- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal whether the applicant has depression.

- ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the applicant has depression.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the applicant has depression.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the applicant has depression.
 - Give an example of potential issues if MedForYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that InsureYou can now determine the number of women in MedForYou's data used to create the AI. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and still protect the information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for MedForYou to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - Give an example of potential issues if MedForYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that InsureYou's employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed applicants by giving them a higher premiums. It is impossible to completely stop favoring brunettes and protect the AI from manipulation. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for MedForYou to choose?**
- i) The AI strongly favors brunettes, and it is highly difficult to manipulate.
 - ii) The AI moderately favors brunettes, and it is moderately difficult to manipulate.
 - iii) The AI slightly favors brunettes, and it is slightly difficult to manipulate.
 - iv) The AI does not favor brunettes, and it is not difficult to manipulate.
 - Give an example of potential issues if MedForYou chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Machine Learning?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.